

Project acronym: EOSC4CANCER
Grant Agreement Number: 101058427
Project full title: A European-wide foundation to accelerate Data-driven Cancer Research
Call identifier: Research infrastructures

D2.3 Survey-based report determining annotation and harmonization needs

Version: 0.3
Status: Final
Dissemination Level: Public
Deliverable Type: *Report*
Due date of deliverable: 30.06.2023 (extended deadline)
Actual submission date: 30.06.2023
Work Package: WP 1/2
Lead partner for this deliverable: UP
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Abstract

Data harmonization plays a crucial role in cancer research by integrating and standardizing heterogeneous data from various sources, enabling meaningful comparisons and analysis. This report presents the findings of a survey conducted to assess the current state, challenges, and needs of data harmonization in cancer research. The survey had a completion rate of 19.7%, with respondents predominantly being male and from the Czech Republic. Key findings reveal that while most respondents have worked with cancer data from multiple sources, only a third have utilized data harmonization methods. Lack of common data standards emerged as the primary challenge, with the level of data harmonization rated as fair. Developing common data standards was identified as the most pressing need. The main benefits of data harmonization were seen as improving comparability of results across studies, while concerns were raised regarding patient re-identification and biased results with the use of machine learning algorithms. Respondents were primarily involved in Genetics/Genomics and/or other -omics research, utilizing electronic health records, biobanks, and reference genomics databases as their primary data sources. The integration of data harmonization into existing systems, improving interoperability, and leveraging technology advances were identified as potential strategies for enhancing data harmonization in cancer research. The survey results underscore the significance of common data standards, addressing challenges in data sharing and standardization, and utilizing advanced technologies to facilitate effective data harmonization in cancer research.

Revision History

Version	Date	Changes made	Author(s)
0.1	20.06.2023	Final draft	Marian Hajduch (UP-MH)
0.2	29.06.2023	Review of the Deliverable	Teresa García (CRG)
0.3	30.06.2023	Final text	Marian Hajduch (UP-MH)

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The survey on data harmonization in cancer research provided valuable insights into the current state, challenges, and needs in this field. The survey had a completion rate of 19.7%, with most respondents being male and from the Czech Republic. Key findings include:

Data Management: Most respondents have worked with cancer data from multiple sources, but only a third have used data harmonization methods. Quality and consistency were identified as important factors in data harmonization.

Challenges and Needs: Lack of common data standards was the most common challenge faced by respondents. The level of data harmonization in cancer research was rated as fair. Developing common data standards was identified as the most pressing need.

Benefits and Risks: The main benefit of data harmonization was seen as improving comparability of results across studies. Machine learning algorithms were seen as potentially beneficial for data harmonization but raised concerns about patient re-identification and biased results.

Cancer Research Involvement: Respondents were primarily involved in Genetics/Genomics and/or other -omics research. Electronic health records, biobanks, and reference genomics databases were the most used data sources.

Interoperability and Integration: Improving interoperability of existing data systems and integrating data harmonization into electronic health records and cancer prevention and screening programs were seen as promising areas for future research.

Precision Medicine and Health Disparities: Data harmonization was seen as a way to improve the identification of biomarkers for targeted therapies and reduce health disparities by including data from diverse populations.

Data Sharing and Standardization: Risks of data breaches or misuse were seen as potential challenges in data sharing and harmonization. Practicality and feasibility were considered important factors when developing data harmonization guidelines.

Technology Advances: Artificial intelligence and machine learning were seen as enabling more efficient and accurate data harmonization.

The survey results highlight the importance of common data standards, interoperability, and addressing challenges in data sharing and standardization in cancer research. Developing common data standards, integrating data harmonization into existing systems, and leveraging technology advances were identified as potential strategies to improve data harmonization in cancer research.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cancer research has witnessed remarkable advancements in recent years, leading to significant breakthroughs in understanding the complex nature of the disease and developing effective treatment strategies. The emergence of big data and the availability of diverse datasets have played a pivotal role in unravelling the mysteries surrounding cancer. However, with this abundance of data comes a critical challenge, which relies on the need to integrate data sets from different sources, also in different formats. To solve this, we need to harmonize data.

Data harmonization refers to the process of integrating and standardizing heterogeneous data from various sources to enable meaningful comparisons and analysis. In cancer research, where data is generated from diverse clinical trials, genomic studies, electronic health records, and population databases, data harmonization becomes a vital necessity. This process allows researchers to leverage the vast amount of information available, thereby enhancing the potential for identifying critical patterns, biomarkers, and therapeutic targets in the fight against cancer.

This report aims to provide an in-depth exploration of the need for data harmonization in cancer research. It will discuss the challenges associated with heterogeneous data sources, highlight the potential benefits of harmonization, and present various approaches and strategies employed in achieving data harmonization. By understanding the significance of data harmonization, researchers can maximize the utility of existing datasets and drive further advancements in cancer research.

Challenges of Heterogeneous Data Sources: The diversity of data sources in cancer research presents a significant challenge for effective analysis and interpretation. Clinical trials, for instance, often employ different protocols, eligibility criteria, and outcome measures, making direct comparisons between studies complex and sometimes unreliable. Additionally, genomic data from various sequencing platforms and technologies may produce non-standardized data formats and differing levels of quality. Genomic analysis can also lead to heterogeneous results due to the discrepancies among different methods that are used to identify genomic alterations. Electronic health records, which contain valuable patient information, often differ in structure, terminologies, and documentation standards across healthcare systems. These disparities in data collection, storage, and representation pose obstacles to efficient integration and analysis.

Moreover, privacy and ethical considerations further complicate data harmonization efforts. Patient data, such as genomic profiles and treatment records, are subject to stringent privacy regulations. Ensuring data security and protecting patient confidentiality while harmonizing datasets across institutions and countries is a critical concern that requires careful attention.

Benefits of Data Harmonization: Despite the challenges, data harmonization offers several significant benefits in cancer research. Firstly, it enables researchers to combine and analyze large-scale datasets, enhancing statistical power and increasing the likelihood of detecting subtle but clinically relevant patterns. Harmonized data facilitates the identification of novel biomarkers, prognostic factors, and therapeutic targets that may have been missed when analyzing individual datasets in isolation.

Furthermore, data harmonization supports meta-analyses and data pooling, enabling researchers to conduct more comprehensive analyses across multiple studies. By aggregating data, researchers can derive more robust conclusions, identify population-specific trends, and overcome limitations posed by small sample sizes in individual studies.

Another advantage of data harmonization is the potential for retrospective analysis. Researchers can retrospectively harmonize historical datasets to examine long-term outcomes, evaluate the effectiveness of past interventions, and generate new hypotheses.

This retrospective approach maximizes the value of existing data and facilitates a deeper understanding of cancer progression and treatment outcomes over time.

Common data models play a crucial role in enabling standardized representation, integration, and analysis of health data across different healthcare systems and research initiatives. One notable example is the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) common data model, which has gained widespread adoption in the field of real-world evidence and comparative effectiveness research. OMOP provides a structured framework for organizing clinical data, including electronic health records, claims data, and administrative data, into a common format. This facilitates the harmonization of diverse datasets and allows researchers to conduct large-scale analyses across multiple data sources.

In addition to OMOP, there are several other common data models being utilized in various research domains. For instance, the Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium (CDISC) offers standardized data models, such as the Study Data Tabulation Model (SDTM), for clinical trial data. These models ensure consistency and interoperability when sharing data across different clinical trials and regulatory submissions.

On an international scale, efforts are being made to establish standardized data models for specific disease areas. The AACR Project GENIE data model aims to integrate genomic and clinical data from cancer patients across multiple institutions, fostering collaboration and advancing precision oncology. Similarly, the minimal dataset for cancer research data at European level has been developed by the 1+MG/B1MG project.

Furthermore, various initiatives in the European Union (EU) and other international organizations are dedicated to promoting interoperability and data sharing. The EU's European Health Data Space (EHDS) initiative aims to create a secure and standardized environment for health data exchange across EU member states. This initiative emphasizes the use of common data models to ensure seamless data integration and facilitate cross-border research collaborations. Additionally, international organizations like the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) are actively working towards the development and implementation of common data models that can be applied globally, enabling data sharing and advancing research in various health domains.

These common data models and ongoing efforts in the EU and international initiatives are instrumental in fostering data harmonization, interoperability, and collaborative research, ultimately leading to improved healthcare outcomes and the advancement of medical knowledge.

Approaches to Data Harmonization: Several approaches and strategies have been developed to address the challenges of data harmonization in cancer research. One commonly employed method is the development and adoption of standardized data collection protocols and reporting guidelines, as exemplified in reporting guidelines for [tumour mutation burdens](#). These guidelines ensure consistent data collection, facilitate data sharing, and improve data quality across studies. Initiatives such as the Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium (CDISC) and the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) play a crucial role in promoting standardized data formats and harmonization practices.

Additionally, computational techniques, including [data integration algorithms and ontology-based methods](#), can assist in harmonizing disparate datasets. These approaches involve mapping data elements to common terminologies.

2 OBJECTIVES OF THE SURVEY ON DATA HARMONIZATION

The survey on data harmonization in cancer research aims to gather valuable insights and information from researchers, clinicians, and other stakeholders involved in cancer research. The specific objectives of the survey are as follows:

- **Assess the current practices and challenges:** The survey aims to understand the current state of data harmonization in cancer research, including the existing practices, methods, and challenges faced by researchers in integrating and harmonizing heterogeneous datasets. By identifying the specific obstacles encountered in data harmonization, the survey seeks to highlight areas that require attention and improvement.
- **Identify common data elements and standards:** The survey aims to identify the common data elements and standards that are crucial for effective data harmonization in cancer research. It seeks to explore the types of data collected, the terminology used, and the specific standards and protocols employed by researchers to ensure interoperability and comparability of datasets. This information will provide insights into the existing standards and potential areas for standardization.
- **Evaluate the impact of data harmonization:** The survey intends to assess the perceived impact and benefits of data harmonization in cancer research. It seeks to gather feedback on the potential improvements achieved through harmonization, such as enhanced data analysis, increased statistical power, and the ability to identify novel insights and patterns. Understanding the positive outcomes resulting from data harmonization can help reinforce its importance and encourage further adoption.
- **Identify barriers and facilitators for data harmonization:** The survey aims to identify the barriers and facilitators that impact the implementation of data harmonization practices in cancer research. It seeks to explore factors such as institutional policies, privacy concerns, technical limitations, resource availability, and collaborative initiatives that influence the successful integration and harmonization of cancer-related datasets. By recognizing these factors, strategies can be developed to overcome barriers and promote facilitators.
- **Gather feedback on potential solutions and best practices:** The survey aims to gather feedback from participants on potential solutions and best practices for data harmonization in cancer research. Participants will be encouraged to share their experiences, insights, and recommendations for improving data harmonization processes.

Overall, the survey on data harmonization in cancer research seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the current landscape, challenges, and opportunities in data harmonization. The survey results will shed light on the most needed areas for harmonization and thus guide further developments within the project. Moreover, it will also help shape future initiatives, policies, and collaborations aimed at advancing data harmonization practices in cancer research, ultimately facilitating more effective analysis, knowledge sharing, and improved patient outcomes.

3 RESULTS

The survey was conducted between 16 May 2023 and 7 June 2023. A total of 213 people visited the survey page, of which 42 completed the survey, translating to an overall completion rate of 19.7%. All participants accessed the survey via a direct link. Survey participants spent an average time of: 2.4% in 5-10 minutes; 69.0% in 10-30 minutes; 14.3% in 30-60 minutes; 14.3% more than 60 minutes. Responses to individual questions are summarized below:

1. Gender of Respondents: Out of the 42 respondents, 59.5% identified as male, 35.7% as female, and 4.8% as other.

2. Country of Research: The majority of respondents (54.8%) were from the Czech Republic, followed by the Netherlands (16.7%), and the United Kingdom (7.1%).

3. Current Role in Cancer Research: Most respondents (73.8%) are identified as researchers, while 28.6% are data analysts and 11.9% are clinicians.

4. Cancer Type Focus: 36.6% of respondents are focused on a specific type of cancer, while the majority (63.4%) are not.

5. Working with Multiple Source Data: The larger part of the respondents (78.6%) have worked with cancer data from multiple sources, while 21.4% have not.

6. Level of Data Harmonization in Cancer Research: The majority of respondents rated the level of data harmonization as fair (47.6%), followed by poor (31%), good (19%), and excellent (2.4%).

7. Challenges in Working with Cancer Data: The most common challenge encountered was the lack of common data standards (81%), followed by data variability (57.1%), and data accessibility (42.9%).

8. Use of Data Harmonization Methods: Only 33.3% of respondents have used data harmonization methods, while 66.7% have not.

9. Important Factors in Data Harmonization: Data quality (73.8%) and data consistency (71.4%) were identified as the most important factors.

10. Ensuring Accuracy and Completeness of Harmonized Data: The majority of respondents ensure accuracy and completeness by performing quality checks and data cleaning (54.8%), while 28.6% use standardized data collection tools. Respondents also provided various answers, including following established guidelines (ACMG/AMP, ARRIVE), using quality checks and data cleaning, comparing practices and guidelines, referring to research articles and published reviews, utilizing data dictionaries, depending on data type, downloading from standard repositories, ensuring the use of established standards including interoperability, tools, QA, QC, data formats, etc., and validating data.

11. Alignment of harmonized cancer data with research question: 31% of respondents ensure that the harmonized cancer data is aligned with the research question by developing a data harmonization plan before data collection, while 59.5% do so by performing data analysis and validation. Participants stated that data variables needed for answering the research question must be collected/extracted from a source system and (re)coded to a(n inter)national standard, following a suitable plan for data collection, creating and following standard operating procedures, controlling vocabulary, conducting exploratory analysis of the data, among other methods.

12. The most pressing data harmonization needs in cancer research: 69% of the respondents felt the most pressing data harmonization need in cancer research was developing common data standards, 54.8% felt improving the interoperability of existing data systems was critical, and 42.9% highlighted the need for harmonizing data from diverse populations.

13. Alignment of harmonization efforts with clinical practice in cancer care: 50% of participants believed data harmonization efforts can be better aligned with clinical practice in cancer care by developing common data standards for clinical and research data. 33.3% favoured integrating data harmonization into electronic health records.

14. Experience with data harmonization in cancer research: The majority (45.2%) of respondents were somewhat familiar with data harmonization in cancer research.

15. Types of cancer research involvement: 71.4% of the respondents were involved in Genetics/Genomics and/or other -omics research, while 31% had participated in clinical trials, and 26.2% in epidemiology.

16. The most challenging aspects of data harmonization in cancer research: were standardizing data elements across different studies (61.9%) and integrating data from different sources (69%).

17. Benefits of data harmonization in cancer research: 76.2% of respondents noted the main benefit as improving the comparability of results across studies.

18. Data resources in cancer research: The most used data sources in cancer research were electronic health records, biobanks, and reference genomics databases and archives, each with a 42.9% response rate.

19. The importance of standardization of data elements across cancer studies: Virtually all respondents consider the standardization of data elements across cancer studies as extremely or somewhat important (69% and 28.6%, respectively).

20. Prioritization of data elements for harmonization: Almost half of the respondents (47.6%) prioritize the data elements to be harmonized based on their relevance to the research question, while others do it based on their availability across different studies or on their potential impact on patient outcomes (23.8% each).

21. Tools and approaches used for data harmonization in cancer research: Common data models were the most popular tool/approach used for data harmonization, selected by 59.5% of respondents. Data dictionaries and controlled vocabularies were also important (28.6% and 23.8, respectively).

22. Data quality and integrity when harmonizing cancer data from multiple sources: 50% of respondents ensure data quality and integrity by implementing data validation and cleaning procedures. Various methods were cited, including implementing data validation, cleaning data, and using standardized data quality metrics.

23. How can funding agencies better support data harmonization efforts in cancer research? The majority of respondents feel that promoting the development of common data standards (38.1%) and encouraging data sharing and collaboration among researchers (31.0%) are the best ways for funding agencies to support data harmonization efforts.

24. Technical issues while harmonizing cancer data from different sources: This was split fairly evenly, with slightly more respondents (52.4%) indicating they had not faced any technical issues.

25. The key factors that hinder the adoption of data harmonization practices: The largest obstacles cited were the difficulty in implementing data standards (42.9%) and lack of awareness or understanding (33.3%).

26. Patient privacy and confidentiality while harmonizing cancer data from different sources: 40.5% of respondents ensure patient privacy and confidentiality by de-identifying the data.

27. Cross-country collaboration to harmonize cancer data: The majority of respondents (61.9%) had not collaborated with researchers from different countries to harmonize cancer data.

28. How can data harmonization efforts be better aligned with patient needs and preferences? A majority (64.3%) suggested incorporating patient-reported outcomes in data harmonization efforts, while 19.0% believed involving patients in the process could align harmonization better with their needs. 16.7% proposed other methods.

29. Potential benefits and risks of using machine learning algorithms for data harmonization in cancer research: Respondents provided textual responses with varied insights. Key benefits mentioned included increased efficiency, identification of new patterns, correlations, better data integration, and automatic processing of big data. Risks raised included patient re-identification, biased results, potential errors, lack of transparency, and the "black box" problem of algorithms.

30. Integration of data harmonization efforts with existing cancer research infrastructure, such as cancer registries and biobanks: A significant majority (61.9%) suggested developing common data standards, while 26.2% proposed establishing data-sharing agreements. The remaining 11.9% recommended other strategies.

31. Integration of data harmonization efforts with clinical care to improve patient outcomes: Over half of the respondents (59.5%) believed integrating data harmonization into electronic health records would improve patient outcomes, while 26.2% preferred using standardized data collection tools. The remaining 14.3% suggested other solutions.

32. Integration of data harmonization efforts with public health initiatives aimed at reducing cancer incidence and mortality: Most respondents (54.8%) proposed incorporating data harmonization into cancer prevention and screening programs. Meanwhile, 31.0% suggested promoting data sharing among public health agencies, with 14.3% providing other ideas.

33. The most promising areas for future research on data harmonization in cancer research: The majority of respondents (61.9%) viewed improving the interoperability of existing data systems as a promising area. Meanwhile, 50.0% saw potential in developing novel data harmonization methods and tools. Identifying new sources of cancer data for harmonization received 14.3% support, and 11.9% recommended other areas.

34. Balance of data harmonization need with the demand for data diversity in cancer research: Nearly 60% of respondents suggested developing flexible data harmonization methods that can accommodate differences in data collection practices. A smaller group (21.4%) recommended using statistical methods to account for differences in data. The remaining 19.0% suggested other strategies.

35. Role of data harmonization in advancing precision medicine in cancer research: Nearly half (47.6%) believed that data harmonization could improve the identification of relevant biomarkers for targeted therapies. Fewer (31.0%) suggested that it could enhance the development of personalized treatment plans. The rest (21.4%) suggested other roles.

36. Alignment of data harmonization efforts to reduce health disparities in cancer outcomes: The majority (57.1%) suggested ensuring that data harmonization efforts include data from diverse populations. Some (31.0%) recommended incorporating data on social determinants of health in data harmonization efforts, while the remaining 11.9% suggested other approaches.

37. Potential challenges or concerns related to data sharing and harmonization in cancer research: Half of the respondents (50.0%) pointed out the risk of data breaches or misuse. A smaller proportion (35.7%) raised concerns about loss of control over data, while 14.3% noted other reasons.

38. The most important factors that should be considered when developing data harmonization guidelines for cancer research: The majority of respondents (54.8%) believe that the most important factor is the "Practicality and feasibility" of the guidelines. This is followed by "Ethical and legal considerations" (21.4%), and "Scientific rigor" (19.0%).

39. Alignment of data harmonization needs with efforts to improve cancer survivorship and quality of life: Responses were equally split between "By incorporating data on patient-reported outcomes in data harmonization efforts" and "By integrating data from survivorship clinics and programs into data harmonization efforts", both garnering 45.2% of responses each.

40. How do you think advances in technology, such as artificial intelligence and machine learning, will impact data harmonization in cancer research? Majority of respondents (69.0%) feel that these advances will enable more efficient and accurate data harmonization.

41. Alignment of data harmonization efforts with demands to improve cancer prevention and early detection: Nearly equal responses were recorded for "By incorporating data from cancer screening programs into data harmonization efforts" (45.2%) and "By integrating data on environmental and lifestyle factors into data harmonization efforts" (40.5%).

42. Participation in a data harmonization project in cancer research: Most respondents (71.4%) have not participated in a data harmonization project in cancer research.

43. Potential benefits of developing a standardized approach to data harmonization in cancer research: Majority of respondents (42.9%) believe that a standardized approach to data harmonization would enhance the reproducibility of research findings.

44. Common data model used for clinical data: Most respondents (51.2%) use in-house models for their clinical data. Some also use unstructured data (29.3%).

45. Ontologies used used for clinical data: The most commonly used ontology was ICD10/ICD11 (31.7%).

46. Type of imaging data collected in cancer research: Most respondents (53.7%) collect Pathology imaging data.

47. Imaging metadata collection from DICOM: More than half (53.7%) of the respondents do collect metadata from DICOM.

48. Collection of the genomic data: Whole genome sequencing and targeted sequencing are the most collected types of genomic data (both 51.2%).

49. Data format in genomic data: The majority of respondents use FASTQ, BAM, and VCF formats (all at 43.9%).

50. Standards for management and representation of the genomic data: The most commonly used standard is the VCF (31.7%).

In general, the survey responses largely highlight the need for data harmonization and emphasize the need for common data standards. However, respondents use diverse common data models, different ontologies, various formats, and a myriad of distinct methodologies to harmonize the data. These contradictory findings, allow us to identify a gap between the recognized necessity for data and metadata harmonization and the current practices, where there is a vast heterogeneity in how researchers approach it. The difficulty in implementing data standards was pointed out as one of the major challenges in the adoption of data harmonization practices, and some reported technical issues during the process. Interestingly, a significant percentage of the participants (~42%) reported little to none experience on harmonizing data for conducting research activities in cancer studies. There was also a high diversity in terms of data types, formats, and models in all areas, including imaging data, genomics data, and clinical data, where a significant number of researchers use free text or internal controlled vocabularies, making it nearly impossible to integrate and interoperate with external datasets.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The survey results provide valuable insights into the state of data harmonization in cancer research. The key findings from the survey are discussed below:

Demographics: The survey had a completion rate of 19.7% from the 213 visitors. The majority of the respondents were male and from the Czech Republic. Most identified as researchers, with a focus on cancer research but not on a specific type of cancer.

Data Management: Most respondents have worked with cancer data from multiple sources. However, only a third have used data harmonization methods. Quality and consistency were identified as the most important factors in data harmonization.

Challenges and Needs: The lack of common data standards was the most common challenge faced by respondents, with the majority rating the level of data harmonization in cancer research as only fair. The need for developing common data standards was also identified as the most pressing data harmonization need.

Benefits and Risks of Data Harmonization: Respondents highlighted the improvement of comparability of results across studies as the main benefit of data harmonization. Regarding the use of machine learning algorithms for data harmonization, respondents highlighted potential benefits such as increased efficiency and the identification of new patterns, but also raised concerns about risks including patient re-identification, biased results, and lack of transparency.

Cancer Research Involvement: Genetics/Genomics and/or other -omics research were the most common areas of involvement. Electronic health records, biobanks, and reference genomics databases and archives were the most used data sources in cancer research.

Interoperability and Integration: The respondents felt that improving the interoperability of existing data systems was a promising area for future research on data harmonization. They also suggested integrating data harmonization into electronic health records, cancer prevention, and screening programs, and saw potential in developing novel data harmonization methods and tools.

Precision Medicine and Health Disparities: Respondents believed that data harmonization could improve the identification of relevant biomarkers for targeted therapies and ensure the inclusion of data from diverse populations to reduce health disparities.

Data Sharing and Standardization: Risks of data breaches or misuse were considered potential challenges related to data sharing and harmonization. Respondents also highlighted the importance of the practicality and feasibility of the guidelines when developing data harmonization guidelines for cancer research.

Technology Advances: Most respondents anticipate that advances in technology, such as artificial intelligence and machine learning, will enable more efficient and accurate data harmonization.

Overall, the survey results suggest a recognition of the importance of data harmonization in cancer research, but also highlight the need for common data standards, improved interoperability, and addressing challenges in data sharing and standardization. The general high diversity in the standards used, for example in the use of common data models, controlled vocabularies and ontologies, manifests the need for harmonization and the dimension of the challenge. Indeed, the development of common data standards, integration into existing systems, and leveraging advances in technology were identified as potential strategies to improve data harmonization in cancer research. Finally, beyond the definition of common data elements and standards, it is important to have mapping efforts to leverage work done across different global sources, which in turn should enable the integration of newly – and standardized – generated datasets with the existing ones.

5 FULL REPORT ON DATA HARMONIZATION SURVEY

General

Survey name	Survey on data harmonization needs
Marian Hajduch, Katerina Sromova, et al.	
English	

Survey URL	https://www.surveio.com/survey/d/V4H0R0I0Q111I7H2Q
First response	16 May 2023
Last response	7 June 2023
Duration	23 days
Total Responses	42

Survey visits

213

Total visits

42

Total completed

0

Total unfinished

171

Displayed only

19.7%

Overall completion rate

Visit History

16 May 2023 - 7 June 2023

Total Hits

- Displayed only (80.3%)
- Completed (19.7%)
- Unfinished (0.0%)

Visit Sources

- Direct link (100.0%)

Average Time of Completion

- 5-10 min. (2.4%)
- 10-30 min. (69.0%)
- 30-60 min. (14.3%)
- >60 min. (14.3%)

Questions and responses

1. What is your gender?

42x answers**0x** unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Male	25	59.5%
Female	15	35.7%
Other...	2	4.8%

2. In which country do you do your research?

42x answers**0x** unanswered

Single choice

- Austria
- Belgium
- Bulgaria
- Croatia
- Czech Republic
- Denmark
- Estonia
- Finland
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- Hungary
- Iceland
- Ireland
- Italy
- Latvia
- Lithuania
- Netherlands
- Norway
- Poland
- Portugal
- Romania
- Slovakia
- Slovenia
- Spain
- Sweden
- Switzerland
- United Kingdom
- Other...

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Austria	1	2.4%
Belgium	1	2.4%
Bulgaria	1	2.4%
Croatia	0	0.0%
Czech Republic	23	54.8%
Denmark	0	0.0%
Estonia	0	0.0%
Finland	0	0.0%
France	1	2.4%
Germany	0	0.0%
Greece	0	0.0%
Hungary	0	0.0%
Iceland	0	0.0%
Ireland	0	0.0%
Italy	2	4.8%
Latvia	1	2.4%
Lithuania	0	0.0%
Netherlands	7	16.7%
Norway	0	0.0%
Poland	0	0.0%
Portugal	0	0.0%
Romania	0	0.0%
Slovakia	0	0.0%

Slovenia	0	0.0%
Spain	2	4.8%
Sweden	0	0.0%
Switzerland	0	0.0%
United Kingdom	3	7.1%
Other...	0	0.0%

3. What is your current role in cancer research?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Multiple choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Clinician	5	11.9%
Researcher	31	73.8%
Data analyst	12	28.6%
Other (please specify)	4	9.5%

4. Are you focused in any particular cancer type?

41x answers**1x** unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Yes, please specify:	15	36.6%
No	26	63.4%

5. Have you ever worked with cancer data from multiple sources?

42x answers **0x** unanswered Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Yes	33	78.6%
No	9	21.4%

6. How would you rate the level of data harmonization in cancer research?

42x answers **0x** unanswered Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Excellent	1	2.4%
Good	8	19.0%
Fair	20	47.6%
Poor	13	31.0%

7. What are the major challenges that you have encountered when working with cancer data from multiple sources?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Multiple choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Data variability	24	57.1%
Lack of common data standards	34	81.0%
Technical issues	13	31.0%
Data accessibility	18	42.9%
Other (please specify)	5	11.9%

8. Have you ever used data harmonization methods to integrate cancer data from multiple sources?

42x answers**0x** unanswered

Single choice

- Yes (please specify your harmonization method(s)/procedure(s))
- No

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Yes (please specify your harmonization method(s)/procedure(s))	14	33.3%
No	28	66.7%

9. What are the most important factors to consider when harmonizing cancer data from different sources?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Multiple choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Data quality	31	73.8%
Data consistency	30	71.4%
Data interoperability	24	57.1%
Other (please specify)	3	7.1%

10. How do you ensure the accuracy and completeness of harmonized cancer data?

42x answers**0x** unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
By using standardized data collection tools	12	28.6%
By performing quality checks and data cleaning	23	54.8%
Other (please specify)	7	16.7%

10b. How do you ensure the accuracy and completeness of harmonized cancer data?

41x answers

1x unanswered

Text answer

- ...
- ACMG/AMP guidelines
- Analysis of empty and outliers
- ARRIVE guidelines
- Assessing integration with other dataset; capacity to benchmark vs gold standard dataset
- availability of data with high quality
- By a set of carefully set quality checks and data cleaning.
- By careful data review
- compare practice and guidelines used in particular teams. Control distribution of factors and studied parameters to be sure about validation.
- Da-Ano 2020 Physics in Medicine and Biology, Harmonization strategies for multicenter radiomics investigations -Mali 2021 Journal of Personalized Medicine, Making radiomics more reproducible across scanner and imaging protocol variazione: A review of harmonization methods
- Data dictionaries
- data check
- Depends on data type.
- Downloading from standard repositories, technical QC, comparison with previously analysed data sets.
- Ensuring the use of established standards including interoperability, tools, QA, QC, data formats, etc. consistently.
- For some variables, one needs to be sure what the limitations are of the collected variable. Was something a primary outcome or a secondary outcome? Is it fair to make one on one comparisons of these?
- <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4675662/>
- I do not know
- I don't have any recommendation
- i dont know
- I dont know
- I don't understand the question!
- Mandatory data elements, controlled vocabulary
- M. D. Wilkinson, M. Dumontier, I. J. Aalbersberg, G. Appleton, M. Axton, A. Baak, N. Blomberg, J.-W. Boiten, L. B. da Silva Santos, P. E. Bourne, et al. "The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship". In: Scientific data 3 (2016).

- N/A
- NCI data harmonization recommendations
- No idea
- none
- not important
- Plotting the data
- Prior to submission, data can be reviewed to check for accuracy and completeness
- quality check, data cleaning
- Same as Q10. I often use light image preprocessing (normalization, resampling, bias correction), but otherwise do not harmonize the data. Rather, I force my AI methods to look through the heterogeneity, as clinicians are also able to do this. In this way, the resulting model is able to perform well on a variable range of data, and thus commonly performs well when externally validated.
- See previous answer: end to end approach, starting at source selection et
- See question 10
- sop and quality control procedures
- use of internal standards during sample measurement powerful data analysis - exclude the batch effect and variability which is occurred during sample processing
- Using a list of minimum common characteristics that must be met by all data sets.
- Usually be recognizing evident errors during the analysis process. Otherwise this is done by bioinformatics experts
- We used data from validated and standardized platforms.
- With data capture tool synchronization and data structuring and validation

11. How do you ensure that the harmonized cancer data is aligned with the research question?

42x answers**0x** unanswered

Single choice

- By developing a data harmonization plan before data collection
- By performing data analysis and validation
- Other (please specify)

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
By developing a data harmonization plan before data collection	13	31.0%
By performing data analysis and validation	25	59.5%
Other (please specify)	4	9.5%

11b. How do you ensure that the harmonized cancer data is aligned with the research question?

41x answers

1x unanswered

Text answer

- --
- ...
- All data variables needed for answering the research question must be collected/extracted from a source system and (re)coded to a(n inter)national standard.
- Appropriate experimental design; accounting for future use of research data; establishment of best practices that fit with needs and capabilities of each research field/question
- Built a CRF for data capture that will enable to answer the research question
- By a data analysis and well suited plan for the collection, where possible.
- by creating and following the standard operating procedure
- By checking the availability of data among sources.
- By looking at the main parameters of interest in the research and that these data have an analogous format (for example, in a single cell analysis, that all the datasets contain information on cell type and that their format is similar).
- By referring to publications and protocols
- Clean and quality control accepted data
- Controlled vocabulary,
- (2x) data analysis
- Data collection and harmonisation planning must be consistent with the original scientific question and the stated hypothesis.
- define the data model and the variables necessary to fit the use case
- During the analysis and validation process
- Exploratory analysis of the data: unsupervised clustering of the data, outlier detection, detection of batch effects.
- Go and read the FDA advisories on this. It all starts with source selection and primary data quality.
- good project plan at the beginning is essential
- <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4511498/>
- I do not know
- I don't have any recommendation
- I dont know
- individual control
- It is part of the data management plan/data collection standard operating procedures

- N/A
- NA
- No my field
- none
- Not sure
- not used
- plan ahead
- QC
- reference standards
- See above
- See question 12
- This needs to be done before starting of project and monitored continuously during project realization.
- Upfront selection of datasets to be combined and harmonized.
- Using standardized data.
- With performing protocols for

12. In your opinion, what are the most pressing data harmonization needs in cancer research?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Multiple choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Developing common data standards	29	69.0%
Improving the interoperability of existing data systems	23	54.8%
Harmonizing data from diverse populations	18	42.9%
Improving the interoperability with analysis systems	11	26.2%
Other (please specify)	4	9.5%

13. How can data harmonization efforts be better aligned with clinical practice in cancer care?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

- By integrating data harmonization into electronic health records
- By developing common data standards for clinical and research data
- Other (please specify)

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
By integrating data harmonization into electronic health records	14	33.3%
By developing common data standards for clinical and research data	21	50.0%
Other (please specify)	7	16.7%

14. How familiar are you with data harmonization in cancer research?

42x answers**0x** unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Very familiar	5	11.9%
Somewhat familiar	19	45.2%
Not very familiar	12	28.6%
Not at all familiar	6	14.3%

15. What types of cancer research have you been involved in?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Multiple choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Epidemiology	11	26.2%
Clinical trials	13	31.0%
Genetics/Genomics and/or other -omics	30	71.4%
Health services research	5	11.9%
Electronic health records	7	16.7%
Other (please specify)	10	23.8%

16. In your opinion, what are the most challenging aspects of data harmonization in cancer research?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Multiple choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Standardizing data elements across different studies	26	61.9%
Integrating data from different sources	29	69.0%
Ensuring data quality and accuracy	23	54.8%
Addressing ethical and legal issues related to data sharing	18	42.9%
Other (please specify)	3	7.1%

17. What are the main benefits of data harmonization in cancer research?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Multiple choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Enhancing the ability to identify risk factors and potential targets for intervention	21	50.0%
Improving the comparability of results across studies	32	76.2%
Reducing redundancy and data fragmentation	15	35.7%
Increasing the statistical power of analyses	20	47.6%
Other (please specify)	5	11.9%

18. What data sources do you typically use in cancer research?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Multiple choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Electronic health records	18	42.9%
Tumor registries	16	38.1%
Biobanks	18	42.9%
Clinical trials databases	12	28.6%
Reference genomics databases and archives, e.g. EGA, dbGAP.	18	42.9%
Major data-oriented consortia, e.g. ICGC	7	16.7%
Other (please specify)	7	16.7%

19. How important is standardization of data elements across cancer studies?

42x answers**0x** unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Extremely important	29	69.0%
Somewhat important	12	28.6%
Not very important	1	2.4%
Not at all important	0	0.0%

20. How do you prioritize which data elements should be harmonized in cancer research?

42x answers**0x** unanswered

Single choice

- Based on their relevance to the research question
- Based on their availability across different studies
- Based on their potential impact on patient outcomes
- Other (please specify)

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Based on their relevance to the research question	20	47.6%
Based on their availability across different studies	10	23.8%
Based on their potential impact on patient outcomes	10	23.8%
Other (please specify)	2	4.8%

21. What tools and approaches have you used for data harmonization in cancer research?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Multiple choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Common data models	25	59.5%
Data dictionaries	12	28.6%
Controlled vocabularies	10	23.8%
Semantic web technologies	5	11.9%
Other (please specify)	8	19.0%

22. How do you ensure data quality and integrity when harmonizing cancer data from multiple sources?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
By using standardized data quality metrics	13	31.0%
By implementing data validation and cleaning procedures	21	50.0%
By performing sensitivity analyses	2	4.8%
Other (please specify)	6	14.3%

22b. How do you ensure data quality and integrity when harmonizing cancer data from multiple sources?

41x answers

1x unanswered

Text answer

- --
- ...
- Again go and read the FDA advisories
- By certain steps of validation, e.g. cross-check
- by doing powerful analyses to reduce the batch effects
- By implementing data validation
- By manual revision
- By validation
- cleaning data
- Cleaning the data before the analysis and using standard data quality metrics and
- Common data models, controlled vocabulary from internationally recognised standards
- data check
- Depends on data type.
- Depends on type of data, but using reference standards
- Exploratory analysis of the data: unsupervised clustering of the data, outlier detection, detection of batch effects.
- <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4511498/>
- i dont know
- I dont know
- Implementation of data validation and quality control checks.
- N/a
- N.A.
- N/A
- (2x) NA
- No idea
- none
- not important
- Performing sensitivity and variability analyses
- quality checks and reach out to data sources in case of quality improvement needs
- Reference datasets
- Report any human-induced errors and propose corrective actions

- see above
- See question 24
- simple comparison, overlap
- standardised ways of checking data quality
- through QC checks
- Using standardized data metrics.
- Validating the findings
- Validation checks/rules.
- With assessment and results validation in accordance with protocols

23. In your opinion, how can funding agencies better support data harmonization efforts in cancer research?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
By providing more funding for data harmonization activities	8	19.0%
By promoting the development of common data standards	16	38.1%
By encouraging data sharing and collaboration among researchers	13	31.0%
Other (please specify)	5	11.9%

24. Have you ever faced any technical issues while harmonizing cancer data from different sources?

42x answers**0x** unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Yes (please describe)	20	47.6%
No	22	52.4%

25. In your opinion, what are the key factors that hinder the adoption of data harmonization practices in cancer research?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Lack of funding	1	2.4%
Lack of awareness or understanding	14	33.3%
Difficulty in implementing data standards	18	42.9%
Resistance from stakeholders	6	14.3%
Other (please specify)	3	7.1%

26. How do you ensure patient privacy and confidentiality while harmonizing cancer data from different sources?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
By de-identifying the data	17	40.5%
By using secure data-sharing platforms	6	14.3%
By obtaining informed consent from patients	10	23.8%
Other (please specify)	9	21.4%

27. Have you ever collaborated with researchers from different countries to harmonize cancer data? If yes, what were the major challenges that you encountered?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Yes (please describe)	16	38.1%
No	26	61.9%

28. How can data harmonization efforts be better aligned with patient needs and preferences?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
By involving patients in the data harmonization process	8	19.0%
By incorporating patient-reported outcomes in data harmonization efforts	27	64.3%
Other (please specify)	7	16.7%

29. What are the potential benefits and risks of using machine learning algorithms for data harmonization in cancer research?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Text answer

- –
- A benefit is increased efficiency for cancer research and for output homogenization. A risk is the uncontrolled combination and acceptance of data from various sources that may not be compatible.
- Benefit: could do some prework to filter out unstructured text to structured text. Risk: context very important, will definitely need a human interpreter check for all variables.
- benefit - Identifying new hypotheses, patterns and correlations
- Benefits: and unbiased data models. Risks: patients re-identification, bias induced by unclear algorithms.
- benefits: automatic processing of big data in cancer research risks: breaking privacy and possibility of reversed identification of individuals
- Benefits: - Better integration and quality of the data. - Simplification of data harmonization processes. - Identification of new biomarkers. Risks: - Lack of transparency about harmonization processes. - Ethical and privacy issues.
- Benefits - easy and quick diagnosis/prognosis Risk -minimal accuracy
- Benefits (exploiting large datasets) Risks (lack of reproducibility)
- Benefits: Identifying cancer types with a high degree of sensitivity and accuracy Risks: Security risk, poor data quality, overfitting, data biasing, lack of strategy and experience
- benefit - speed and objective assement based on parameters risk - bias or false results
- benefits - reduce the risk of human fault risks - the algorithms cannot think and could create some non-senses
- Benefits - Risks -
- Benefits - stronger results, better incorporation of the results across different populations/risk factors/..., identifying less pronounce results Risks - false positive results
- Benefits - the possibility of harmonizing the already generated data
- Benefits: use of big data for development harmonization data models
- Better analysis of the data, finding correlations between various features. Negative: potential of over-fitting and results of lower quality.
- biais
- Can't say definitively but we need an innovative way to manage data curation
- Dferent data inputs and lack of standardized process flow

- Generally, ai driven harmonisation is bullshit: garbage in, garbage out problem. There are some limited exceptions, such as automation of RECIST calling from images for real world data
- Generation of realistic data models, patient re-identification, the models may be difficult to interpret, patient consent
- <https://arxiv.org/abs/2109.09658>: lack of Fairness, Universality, Traceability, Usability, Robustness, and Explainability
- (2x) i dont know
- I don't know
- I dont know
- Insufficient quality of the original data
- Lack of transparency
- NA
- no idea
- No idea.
- Not sure
- not used
- Potential mistake when you have anonymized data. You will never find the mistake.
- problematic and difficult control by skilled researcher not to have inverted results
- Pro: maximise data use to generate new insights; Con: algorithms bias; black box leading to miss trust
- risk of errors; re-identifying individuals
- risk - patient re- identification
- Saving time
- The discovery of new dependencies and relationships, the risk is misuse of data to identify patients and loss of privacy
- The main benefit would be to speed up the process and to develop user friendly standards and interface. The main risk would be resistance of doctors and the incompatibility with currently used hospital systems.

30. How can data harmonization efforts be better integrated with existing cancer research infrastructure, such as cancer registries and biobanks?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

- By developing common data standards
- By establishing data-sharing agreements
- Other (please specify)

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
By developing common data standards	26	61.9%
By establishing data-sharing agreements	11	26.2%
Other (please specify)	5	11.9%

31. How can data harmonization efforts be better integrated with clinical care to improve patient outcomes?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
By using standardized data collection tools	11	26.2%
By integrating data harmonization into electronic health records	25	59.5%
Other (please specify)	6	14.3%

32. How can data harmonization efforts be better integrated with public health initiatives aimed at reducing cancer incidence and mortality?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
By promoting data sharing among public health agencies	13	31.0%
By incorporating data harmonization into cancer prevention and screening programs	23	54.8%
Other (please specify)	6	14.3%

33. What are the most promising areas for future research on data harmonization in cancer research?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Multiple choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Developing novel data harmonization methods and tools	21	50.0%
Improving the interoperability of existing data systems	26	61.9%
Identifying new sources of cancer data for harmonization	6	14.3%
Other (please specify)	5	11.9%

34. How do you balance the need for data harmonization with the need for data diversity in cancer research?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

- By developing flexible data harmonization methods that can accommodate differences in data collection practices
- By using statistical methods to account for differences in data
- Other (please specify)

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
By developing flexible data harmonization methods that can accommodate differences in data collection practices	25	59.5%
By using statistical methods to account for differences in data	9	21.4%
Other (please specify)	8	19.0%

35. What role do you think data harmonization can play in advancing precision medicine in cancer research?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Improving the identification of relevant biomarkers for targeted therapies	20	47.6%
Enhancing the development of personalized treatment plans	13	31.0%
Other (please specify)	9	21.4%

36. How can data harmonization efforts be better aligned with efforts to reduce health disparities in cancer outcomes?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

- By incorporating data on social determinants of health in data harmonization efforts
- By ensuring that data harmonization efforts include data from diverse populations
- Other (please specify)

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
By incorporating data on social determinants of health in data harmonization efforts	13	31.0%
By ensuring that data harmonization efforts include data from diverse populations	24	57.1%
Other (please specify)	5	11.9%

37. What are some potential challenges or concerns related to data sharing and harmonization in cancer research?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Risk of data breaches or misuse	21	50.0%
Loss of control over data	15	35.7%
Other (please specify)	6	14.3%

38. In your opinion, what are the most important factors that should be considered when developing data harmonization guidelines for cancer research?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Scientific rigor	8	19.0%
Ethical and legal considerations	9	21.4%
Practicality and feasibility	23	54.8%
Other (please specify)	2	4.8%

39. How can data harmonization efforts be better aligned with efforts to improve cancer survivorship and quality of life?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

- By incorporating data on patient-reported outcomes in data harmonization efforts
- By integrating data from survivorship clinics and programs into data harmonization efforts
- Other (please specify)

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
By incorporating data on patient-reported outcomes in data harmonization efforts	19	45.2%
By integrating data from survivorship clinics and programs into data harmonization efforts	19	45.2%
Other (please specify)	4	9.5%

40. How do you think advances in technology, such as artificial intelligence and machine learning, will impact data harmonization in cancer research?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Enabling more efficient and accurate data harmonization	29	69.0%
Introducing new ethical and legal considerations	7	16.7%
Other (please specify)	6	14.3%

41. How can data harmonization efforts be better aligned with efforts to improve cancer prevention and early detection?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
By incorporating data from cancer screening programs into data harmonization efforts	19	45.2%
By integrating data on environmental and lifestyle factors into data harmonization efforts	17	40.5%
Other (please specify)	6	14.3%

42. Have you ever participated in a data harmonization project in cancer research? If yes, please describe your experience.

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Yes (please describe)	12	28.6%
No	30	71.4%

43. What are some potential benefits of developing a standardized approach to data harmonization in cancer research?

42x answers

0x unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Enhancing the reproducibility of research findings	18	42.9%
Facilitating data sharing and collaboration among researchers	9	21.4%
Improving the quality and accuracy of cancer data	10	23.8%
Other (please specify)	5	11.9%

44. For the clinical data, what is the common data model used?

41x answers

1x unanswered

Multiple choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
In-house models	21	51.2%
Not structured data	12	29.3%
GA4GH Phenopackets	0	0.0%
HL7 FHIR	6	14.6%
mCode	3	7.3%
OMOP	5	12.2%
openEHR	6	14.6%
Other (please specify)	10	24.4%

45. For the clinical data, which are the ontologies used?

41x answers

1x unanswered

Multiple choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
SNOMED CT	9	22.0%
LOINC	3	7.3%
ICD10/ICD11	13	31.7%
ICD-O3	6	14.6%
NCIt	2	4.9%
RxNorm	2	4.9%
ATC (level)	3	7.3%
RadLEx	2	4.9%
ACR/RADS	1	2.4%
Our data is in free text	12	29.3%
Our data is represented an internal controlled vocabulary	11	26.8%
Other (please specify)	13	31.7%

46. For the imaging data, what is the imaging data collected?

41x answers

1x unanswered

Multiple choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
We do not collect/use any imaging data for research	10	24.4%
CT	17	41.5%
MRI	16	39.0%
X-Ray	6	14.6%
US	3	7.3%
MG	3	7.3%
PET	13	31.7%
RT	3	7.3%
Pathology	22	53.7%
Other (please specify)	4	9.8%

47. Regarding imaging data, is metadata collected from DICOM

41x answers

1x unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Yes	22	53.7%
If not, please specify	19	46.3%

48. For the genomic data, what is the genomic data collected?

41x answers

1x unanswered

Multiple choice

58

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
We do not collect/use any genomics data for research	7	17.1%
Whole genome sequencing	21	51.2%
Targeted sequencing	21	51.2%
Whole Exome sequencing	16	39.0%
RNA sequencing	24	58.5%
Methylation	13	31.7%
Other (please specify)	5	12.2%

49. For the genomic data, which is the genomic data format?

41x answers

1x unanswered

Multiple choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
We do not collect	9	22.0%
FASTQ	18	43.9%
BAM	18	43.9%
VCF	18	43.9%
MAF	5	12.2%
Other (please specify)	11	26.8%

50. For management and representation of the genomic data, do you use any particular standard?

41x answers

1x unanswered

Multiple choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
We do not use any	10	24.4%
In-house models and databases	10	24.4%
None	6	14.6%
VCF	13	31.7%
GA4GH Variation Representation (VRS)	1	2.4%
Sequence Ontology	3	7.3%
HUGO Gene Nomenclature	7	17.1%
HGVS Sequence Variance Nomenclature	6	14.6%

51. For the cancer registries, Is your data model compliant with ENCR recommendations?

41x answers

1x unanswered

Single choice

ANSWER	RESPONSES	RATIO
Yes	17	41.5%
If not, please specify:	24	58.5%

Survey settings

Allow multiple submissions?	Yes
Allow return to previous questions?	Yes
123 Display question numbers?	Yes
Receive response notifications by e-mail?	No
Password protection?	No
IP restriction?	No